

ON THE STUDY OF SPEECH AND ITS CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES IN WORLD LINGUISTICS

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Annotatsiya. This article deals with research on the issue of speech in English and Uzbek languages and the research of communicative qualities of speech.

Kalit so'zlar: culture, speech, verbal, non-verbal, grammatical norms.

In order for the speech to be good in every way, it sets certain requirements for itself. These requirements are called the main qualities and characteristics of speech. They are correctness, accuracy, logicity, effectiveness, cleanliness, comprehensibility and appropriateness of the speech.

1. Correctness of speech. V.Y. Kostomarov writes "Correctness as a necessary and first condition of the culture of speech, strictly and precisely conforms to the norms of the literary language accepted at a certain time, acquires its pronunciation, orthographic vocabulary and grammatical norms. it is necessary to understand". Correctness of speech is its most important communicative quality. If the speech is not correct, other communicative qualities will also be destroyed. If the structure of the speech is not correct, it also damages its logic, accuracy, and purposefulness. In order for the speech to be correct, it mainly requires strict adherence to two norms - accent and grammatical norms. It should not be forgotten that sometimes the meaning of words can change with the shift of emphasis. This also leads to speech disorders: Olma – olma, hozir – hozir, o'quvchimiz – o'quvchimiz, yangi – yangi va h.k.

The logical accent that falls on one word in a sentence has a great service in differentiating the meaning. Adhering to the grammatical norm means correct use of the rules of sentence formation, not making mistakes when adding stems and suffixes, using agreement suffixes in their place, possessive and participle compatibility, the laws of connecting secondary fragments to them are understood. [1].

2. The accuracy of the speech is that the word is completely consistent with the reality it expresses. Clarity has long been known as one of the important qualities of speech. Both Western thinkers and Eastern scientists considered accuracy to be the first condition of speech qualities. Aristotle said:

"If the speech is unclear, it will not achieve the goal", Kaikovus: "O child, know the face and back of the word, follow them, speak meaningfully when you speak, this is the essence of eloquence is a symptom. If you don't know the meaning of a word when you speak, you will be like a double..." he says. Clarity, as a quality of speech, is related to the ability to express clearly, the meaning of the subject of speech, and knowledge of the meanings of words used in speech. If the speaker knows well the subject of the speech he wants to think about, chooses appropriate words for it and assigns tasks corresponding to the meanings of the words he chooses, then the speech will be clear. Clarity is of two kinds: clarity of object and clarity of concept.

3. The logic of speech is closely related to its main qualities of correctness and accuracy. Because it is natural that both a grammatically incorrect speech and an unsuccessfully chosen lexical unit to express an idea lead to a violation of logic. Violation of logical consistency leads to incompleteness of the idea expressed to the listener and reader, and sometimes it is not understood at all. As a result of carelessness in structuring the speech, sometimes even illogicality occurs. consider the following example: "Farm enthusiasts fulfill six-month state milk sales plans ahead of schedule (from newspaper). In the sentence, the order of words is not correct, the combination of "six months" does not come after the word "sale" and the logic is broken, even the wrong idea is expressed. The logicity of the concept requires that there is an intellectual sequence, a logical consistency in a separate text. However, this demand cannot be expressed in all aspects of the speech process. For example: let's take a look at how this requirement is followed in the styles of task, especially in the styles of scientific and artistic speech. Works written in a scientific style have a coherent structure. It has an introduction, a main part and a conclusion, which are united into a single nation. The ideas expressed in the text are expressed in strict consistency. The structure of artistic speech is a little different. Let's say that thoughts are being expressed at one time, and suddenly there is a break, and now other events are being narrated.

Although this may seem like a violation of logical consistency, it is not. In works of art, in particular, in genres such as short story and novel, the wide planning requires the construction of the image in this way. It becomes clear at the end of such works that it is not logically damaged. In conclusion, by the logic of the speech, we understand the speech that is structured on the basis of a whole system, the development of thoughts is consistent, and every word and phrase is used in accordance with the specific purpose.

4. Cleanliness of speech. Cleanliness of speech means, first of all, that it does not conform to the linguistic norm of the literary language. In fact, a good, ideal speech should be composed in accordance with the requirements of the modern Uzbek literary language, and should be free of various language and non-literary language elements.

This is the linguistic side of the issue, and the non-linguistic aspects of speech purity are no less important. The linguistic elements that destroy the purity of our speech are mainly dialectisms and barbarisms.

True, they must be used in our language, it cannot be done without it. Because, in the language of fiction literature, dialectics and barbarisms can fulfill a certain artistic and aesthetic task, and serve to realize a certain idea and intention of the author. For example, it is even necessary to refer to dialectisms and barbarisms when referring to the origin of the hero of the work or trying to give a national character.

For instance: "Yoshulli, saning qizing bunda gatirilmagan. Ova, yoshulli. San manglayi qara batkirdor, na sababda mundoq yomon so'zlarni elga tarqatding" (Mirmuxsin).

In the following example, barbarisms - foreign words helped the writer to create a character, just as dialectisms served to give regional character in this example. "Dobora" went to work again, (swearing, - he said, don't come, stop, push!) [2].

So, the speaker is required to act according to the situation, and it is his task to try to fully convey the idea he wants to express to the audience. So, what kind of speech should be understood as an effective speech? B. N. Golovin defines it as follows: "Effective speech refers to the characteristics of speech construction that attract the attention and interest of the listener and reader, and the speech with these characteristics is considered effective." Speaking in a language that the public can understand, being able to convince them is one of the main conditions for speakers. For this, as mentioned above, in addition to knowing the topic well, there should be a clearly defined plan for its presentation. It is necessary to organize the thoughts in the speech in the first and second order, connect them, introduce the plan of the speech to the audience first, and connect the sentence. Timing is one of the virtues of public speaking. Because the audience will not get bored if the speaking time is announced in advance and followed, if possible, if it ends a little earlier. The attitude of the speaker to his speech is also important, because only then can we avoid dry formality. The communication between the speaker and the listener will be good. If the speaker

tries to prove his ideas on the basis of examples taken from his own or the audience's life, if he expresses his subjective opinion on the topic, the speech will be more effective.

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